

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Storyline of Renewable Energy pilot study
Deliverable number	D51 (Del. Rel. No. D10.8)
Planned delivery date	31/07/2025
Actual date of issue	30/06/2025
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	BSC
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

Report presenting the renewable energy pilot study as a coherent storyline which provides a unity to physical and social components.

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WP10

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents a novel approach to integrating high-resolution Earth-system model outputs with participatory scenario development to support the renewable energy transition in Europe. Conducted within the simulations generated by nextGEMS, the study explores how storm-resolving Earth system models (SR-ESMs) can inform national energy planning when combined with stakeholder-driven storylines.

To test the methodology, we conducted a proof-of-concept case study focusing on Spain's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), a strategic document outlining the country's decarbonization pathway, which is part of a legal framework present in all EU Member States. While such plans are key instruments for climate mitigation, they often don't consider the impacts of climate change on renewable energy sources and the socio-political factors that influence public acceptance and their overall implementation.

To address these limitations, the project conducted a series of workshops involving energy stakeholders from government, academia, industry, and civil society. Through a co-production process, three storylines were developed—Actual, Integrative, and Distributive—each reflecting different visions of the future energy transition. These qualitative narratives were then used to guide and constrain SR-ESM outputs, which included projections of wind and solar resource availability across Spain and applying different masks.

By combining scenario-based, discourse-analytical, and physical climate storyline methodologies, the study provides proof of concept for how SR-ESMs can support policy decisions even before full model readiness is achieved. Results show that stakeholders value spatially detailed model outputs but require the role of boundary actors to interpret them and eventually integrate them into decision-making. The storyline method also facilitated inclusive dialogue on contested aspects of the energy transition, such as centralization vs. decentralization and trade-offs between efficiency and equity.

Overall, the policy implications are that km-scale Earth System Models can be a great ally to countries as tools for the energy transition and supporting regional differentiation in energy planning. National energy plans should integrate climate variability and extremes in order to create resilient energy systems. We have evidenced, also, how participatory methods can improve social acceptance and the relevance of modeling outputs. Finally, and to conclude, co-produced storylines offer a mechanism to align science, policy, and public concerns. Future research should focus on operationalising such approaches and validating their added value.

To conclude, this work contributes to bridging the knowledge-action gap in climate science by emphasizing co-production, interdisciplinarity, and actionable modeling. It suggests that early engagement of societal actors and integration of novel climate information can enhance the usability and robustness of energy transition strategies, as well as make km-scale modelling efforts more fit-for-purpose.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	no

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	yes
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	yes
Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)	no

Synergies

This work draws on and contributes to several areas within nextGEMS. It relies on the storm-resolving simulations developed in WP2 and WP3 and connects closely with WP8 and WP10 through its co-production approach and focus on societal relevance. The stakeholder engagement process and scenario development support WP10's science-society objectives

1 Introduction

The NextGEMS project aims to advance climate modeling by developing and applying storm-resolving Earth system models (SR-ESMs) at unprecedented kilometer-scale resolution. These scientific and technological advances present new opportunities to link high-resolution climate data with societal processes, particularly those involving deep uncertainty and complex socio-technical transitions such as the shift toward renewable energy.

Decarbonization strategies are central in supranational policy frameworks, including the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal. At the national level and across the EU, Member States are required to submit 10-year national energy and climate plans (NECPs), which define trajectories for emission reductions and renewable energy deployment. However, these plans often neglect the impacts of climate change on renewable resource availability, as well as the energy demand which is expected to increase as a result of climate change trends.

This deliverable presents a proof of concept for using SR-ESMs in conjunction with co-produced scenario storylines to support robust energy planning under deep uncertainty. The work is based on a literature review, a series of participatory workshops with the nextGEMS community and stakeholders from the energy sector, and an integration of nextGEMS simulation outputs through storyline methodologies. To conduct the proof of concept, we selected as a case study the Spanish Energy and Climate Integrated Plan, a policy instrument of relevance in all EU Member States, where we investigate how climate model outputs and stakeholder narratives can inform alternative visions for the energy transition. Also, we discuss how these societal processes can support modeling efforts moving forward.

2 Background: the role of storylines in climate science

Storylines have emerged as an increasingly relevant tool in climate science for bridging the usability gap between scientific outputs and decision-making contexts. A semi-systematic literature review identified three main approaches (Baulenas et al., 2023) :

- Scenario-based storylines (e.g., SSPs) combine qualitative narratives with quantitative modeling.
- Discourse-analytical storylines examine the narratives and framings actors use and their consequences.
- Physical climate storylines explore plausible chains of physical climate events under different conditions.

In these different approaches, 'storylines' have all a different meaning. Also, they share a common aim of making future climate developments more understandable and relevant to decision-making. However, these approaches vary significantly in their theoretical underpinnings, methods, and degrees of stakeholder engagement. This diversity can be both a strength and a limitation, especially when aiming to bridge the persistent usability gap between climate science

and climate action (Knutti, 2019).

Scenario-based approaches (SB) are the most established and widely used, particularly through the influence of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). In these approaches, storylines are defined as qualitative descriptions of plausible future world evolutions and serve as a basis for constructing quantitative scenarios, such as the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) (IPCC, 2023). These approaches are particularly valuable for decision-making because they integrate socio-economic and environmental dimensions and provide standardized frameworks that can be used across multiple models and regions. However, their practical utility has been criticized for several reasons. First, the construction of scenarios often lacks transparency, especially regarding how the range of plausible futures is defined and whose perspectives are included. Second, these approaches frequently rely on top-down processes with limited or tokenistic stakeholder involvement, which can lead to outputs that are poorly aligned with local needs or political realities. Moreover, early iterations of SSPs have been criticized for their underrepresentation of Global South perspectives and for reinforcing dominant narratives centered on economic growth (Mitter et al., 2019). While recent efforts have incorporated more participatory and co-production elements, these remain the exception rather than the rule.

Discourse-analytical approaches (DAA), by contrast, originate in the social sciences and focus on how meaning, language, and power shape climate policy and societal responses. In this tradition, storylines are seen as condensed narratives that use metaphors to frame complex phenomena and organize collective meaning (Hajer, 1995). Rather than projecting futures through models, discourse-analytical work examines how narratives influence policy development, institutional change, and public understanding. This approach is beneficial for uncovering the value-laden and contested nature of climate discourses and for highlighting whose voices are included or marginalized in the framing of climate issues. It supports decision-making by illuminating the political dynamics behind climate policies and by helping actors reflect on their framing assumptions (Bastakoti and Davidsen, 2017). However, DAA is often criticized for its limited scalability and generalizability. Because discourse is context-dependent and inherently situated, findings may be difficult to translate across regions or policy levels. Furthermore, DAA typically lacks the modeling tools and empirical projections that many policymakers expect from climate science, which may reduce its perceived relevance for certain types of decision-making.

Physical climate storylines (PCS) represent the most recent addition to the climate science literature, emerging in the past decade with foundational work by Shepherd (2018). This approach defines storylines as physically self-consistent unfoldings of past or plausible future events. Unlike probabilistic climate models that rely on ensemble means, PCS focus on specific events or sequences—such as extreme heatwaves or floods—and examine their plausible evolution under changing boundary conditions. The central premise is that presenting decision-makers with a conditional set of “what-if” events can be more effective for risk assessment and planning than abstract probabilities (Shepherd et al., 2018). PCS offer four major strengths: they make risks more tangible by appealing to episodic memory; they shift attention from likelihood to consequences; they allow for the separate treatment of thermodynamic and dynamic uncertainties; and they promote physical understanding of climate processes. However, PCS have its limitations. Most applications remain confined within the physical sciences, often omitting

socioeconomic dimensions and stakeholder input. As a result, they may struggle to connect with real-world decision-making contexts unless coupled with interdisciplinary and participatory methods. Furthermore, PCS has faced criticism from traditional attribution science communities for departing from probabilistic norms, though proponents argue that both approaches can be complementary (Lloyd and Oreskes, 2018).

While each approach has unique contributions, Baulenas et al. (2023) emphasize the need for cross-pollination to enhance the relevance and usability of climate storylines. Scenario-based methods could benefit from the contextual awareness and participatory sensitivity of discourse analysis, while PCS would gain legitimacy and applicability by involving users in the selection and interpretation of events. Discourse-analytical studies, in turn, might increase their policy relevance by incorporating modeling or simulation techniques. Across all approaches, the authors advocate for mixed-method designs, broader transdisciplinary teams, and more inclusive stakeholder engagement, particularly in the selection and co-production of storylines. They also suggest expanding quality criteria beyond the standard of “plausibility” to include dimensions such as salience, legitimacy, richness, and creativity, following Mitter et al. (2019).

In conclusion, the concept of storylines holds significant promise for supporting climate adaptation, mitigation, and risk assessment. However, realizing this potential depends on fostering greater methodological openness and collaboration among the scholarly communities currently working in parallel. By integrating good practices from scenario-based, discourse-analytical, and physical climate storyline approaches, climate science can produce more actionable and socially robust knowledge that bridges the gap between science and decision-making.

To leverage the strengths of each whilst mitigating their weaknesses, this study combines elements from all three approaches. We use narrative co-production with stakeholders (discourse-analytical), develop scenario framings (scenario-based), and integrate SR-ESM outputs (physical storylines) to test how they can be brought together to support energy policy and modelling efforts equally.

3 Methods

3.1 Case study

We use the Spanish National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) as a case study. Spain presents an ideal testbed as it is representative of the narratives surrounding the renewable energy transition in European contexts. As we wanted to conduct participatory methodologies, a national-level approach enabled access to a wide range of actors key to the energy transition. We describe the process of stakeholder selection next.

3.2 Stakeholder mapping and engagement

The first step of the study was to conduct a literature review to unravel the discourses around the energy transition. In this literature review, factors such as public acceptance (movements

against renewable energy), trade-offs with biodiversity, or the creation of sacrifice zones emerged.

After gathering these narratives, we conducted a stakeholder mapping that would represent them. Other main criteria were: the representation of the most important stakeholder categories, including government, private, and third sectors, as well as academia, and involvement of representatives of the energy sector’s supply chain (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of stakeholders by categories (n=67)

Stakeholders were all contacted, and we conducted small, unstructured interviews to understand the climate information needs and interest for km-scale ESMs. After, they were invited to the participatory workshops.

The storyline development process involved three participatory workshops: the first conducted with the nextGEMS community during the 2nd hackathon (Vienna), the second conducted with energy stakeholders during the 3rd hackathon (Madrid), and the third conducted two years later in the same premises of the University Complutense of Madrid, and labelled the "integration" workshop. The second workshop, attended by 23 external participants, generated the storylines through co-production with diverse stakeholders, including national-level governmental bodies, energy providers, researchers, NGOs, and civil society actors. The last workshop, with 30 external participants, the majority of whom had attended also the second workshop, presented the simulation results and discussed ways in which these simulations can inform policy and

planning.

The workshops were structured around the evaluation and refinement of three initial storylines:

1. Actual scenario – reflecting current policy trajectories.
2. Integrative scenario – emphasizing trade-offs with biodiversity.
3. Distributive scenario – focusing on a decentralized and community-based energy transition.

Figure 2 below displays how the debate was structured in the final integration workshop:

Figure 2: Screenshot of the material used during the 3rd workshop (in Spanish)

For more details on the first two participatory workshops, please refer to Baulenas and Bojovic, 2023.

3.3 Climate simulations

The kilometre-scale Earth system models (km-ESMs) used in this study were developed and implemented under the NextGEMS project. The ICON and IFS-FESOM simulations spanned

from 2020 to 2050 and followed the SSP3-7.0 scenario for greenhouse gas concentrations. The models provided hourly or sub-hourly data on key variables, including wind speed and solar radiation, which were processed to compute capacity factors for wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) energy production over mainland Spain and the Balearic Islands. For wind energy, ICON 10-metre wind speed data were extrapolated to 100 metres using a logarithmic profile, while IFS-FESOM provided wind speeds at 100 metres directly. The capacity factors were derived using the power curve of a standard wind turbine model (Vestas V112-3MW). For solar PV, capacity factors were calculated from global horizontal irradiance, air temperature, wind speed, and precipitation, taking into account soiling effects and temperature-dependent panel efficiency, with cleaning triggered by precipitation events.

The simulations were used to explore the spatial and temporal evolution of renewable energy potential under the different stakeholder co-produced storyline scenarios. These included an “actual” scenario aligned with current deployment patterns, an “integrative” scenario prioritizing biodiversity protection, and a “distributed” scenario emphasizing rooftop solar potential.

The “actual” scenario were the outputs of the simulations as explained above. However, to operationalise the other two scenarios, we used spatial masking. For choosing the masks for the “integrative” scenario - which, for biodiversity concerns, protects areas of Spain from hosting RE facilities - we followed a proposition from the Spanish Ministry of the Ecological Transition: zonation areas¹. The spatial outputs of the models were masked according to the Ministry’s proposed environmental sensitivity classifications and protected areas (e.g., Natura 2000) to quantify the impact of excluding these zones from renewable energy capacity factors. The km-scale resolution enabled a detailed assessment of how fine-scale climate processes, such as regional wind and solar patterns, may influence future energy production potentials under varying societal choices.

For the “distributed” scenario, we used data from all roof surfaces and subsequently computed the fraction of each model grid cell covered by roof surfaces suitable for the installation of PV panels. In this scenario, we only consider the PV potential of roof surfaces.

The work on the kilometre-scale Earth system model simulations was carried out in close collaboration with partners from the nextGEMS project. In particular, colleagues from Wageningen University and Research, the University of Bern, the University of Vienna, and the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology contributed to the development, execution, and analysis of the km-scale model experiments. Their expertise was instrumental in producing and interpreting the high-resolution simulations that underpin the assessment of renewable energy potentials explored in this study. This collaborative effort reflects the interdisciplinary and transnational nature of NextGEMS, which aims to advance climate modelling in support of societal decision-making.

For more details about the data and methods used for this study, please refer to the submitted publication related to this deliverable Baulenas et al., 2025.

¹Please, refer to: https://www.miteco.gob.es/en/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/evaluacion-ambiental/zonificacion_ambiental_energias_renovables.html

4 Results

This section presents the results of the participatory, interdisciplinary process that combined qualitative scenario development with quantitative km-scale Earth system model (ESM) simulations. As mentioned above, the aim was to explore how high-resolution climate modeling can support renewable energy planning and how participatory methods can increase the societal relevance and usability of these emerging modeling tools. The results are presented in three phases: storyline co-production, translation into physical climate constraints, and integration into decision-making.

Co-production of energy transition storylines

During the participatory workshop, stakeholders representing governmental bodies, the private sector actors, civil society, and researchers collaboratively developed three narrative-based scenarios for Spain's energy transition. These were referred to as the actual, the integrative, and the distributed storylines. Each storyline reflected a different logic for navigating the transition to renewable energy: the actual scenario followed the current policy trajectory prioritising rapid expansion; the integrative scenario added environmental safeguards by restricting renewable installations in biodiversity-sensitive areas; and the distributed scenario envisioned a decentralised system led by energy communities and citizen participation. These scenarios have some representation in proposed legislation in the case study.

The discussions revealed that each storyline carried distinct trade-offs. The actual scenario was perceived as more feasible in the short term but raised concerns about replicating existing inequalities and unsustainable resource dependencies. The integrative scenario was considered more aligned with environmental and territorial planning goals but slower to implement and dependent on complex regulatory changes. The distributed scenario was seen as very positive for its emphasis on equity and local engagement, yet faced concerns about technical efficiency, system integration, and the pace of deployment to reach the transition goals. Importantly, stakeholders noted that these narratives helped reveal not only different technical pathways but also interdependencies amongst them.

Physical translation through km-scale climate simulations

To assess the physical feasibility of each storyline, we translated their spatial constraints into km-scale climate simulations from the two nextGEMS models: ICON and IFS-FESOM. The simulations spanned the period from 2020–2050 under the SSP3-7.0 scenario. For both wind and solar energy, capacity factors were computed to reflect changes in renewable energy potential under evolving climate conditions.

Figure 3 and 4 show the capacity factor maps that were generated by the collaboration with nextGEMS partners (authors of figure 3: Edgar Dolores-Tesillos, Bern University; and Figure 4: Menno Veerman, Wageningen University and Research). The figures displays the decadal mean capacity factors of the main IFS and ICON simulations. Generally the differences between decades (e.g. from 2020-2029 to 2040-2049, or from IFS-hist to IFS) are much smaller than differences between the models, indicating that your choice of model impacts PV production more than a bit of climate change.

Figure 3: Annual mean onshore wind capacity factors based on the IFS-FESOM (top row) and ICON (bottom row) simulations, for the first decade of the simulations (2020-2029, left column) and changes in annual mean capacity factor relative to first decade for 2030-2039 (middle column) and 2040-2049 (right column)

The results show noticeable differences between the models. For wind energy, ICON projected a decrease in capacity factors during the 2030s followed by a slight rebound in the 2040s, while IFS-FESOM simulated an increase in the 2030s and a drop thereafter. However, both models indicated a decline in wind potential in southern Spain by the 2040s. For solar energy, ICON suggested a general increase in capacity factors across most of Spain, whereas IFS-FESOM pointed to declines, especially in the south. These differences were partly linked to the treatment of dust accumulation and soiling in IFS-FESOM, as well as to internal climate variability. The difference in modeling outputs by the two models was used to explain how climate modeling works more generally, as the technical background of the participants varied greatly. Thus, it was useful to engage in science communication and literacy efforts.

We then applied spatial constraints corresponding to each storyline. In the integrative scenario, we masked Natura 2000 sites and areas with high environmental sensitivity, reducing the available area for energy installations. This resulted in a decrease in mean capacity factors by 30 to 50 percent across both energy types, primarily due to reduced land availability rather than lower resource potential. In the distributed scenario, which assumed only rooftop PV installations, capacity factors dropped by two orders of magnitude, underscoring the limitations of a fully urban-based deployment model. These physical storylines helped make visible the implications of different choices about land use, conservation, and decentralisation.

Integration into decision-making processes

In the final workshop, stakeholders were invited to reflect on the results of the climate simulations and to discuss how such information could support their decision-making within each storyline. The integration phase highlighted the different temporal and governance logics associated with each scenario. In the actual scenario, priorities focused on scaling up existing efforts, improving storage and grid infrastructure, and managing energy surpluses. In the integrative scenario, decisions revolved around reconciling energy goals with biodiversity protection, including the

Figure 4: Annual mean solar photovoltaics (PV) capacity factors, based on the IFS-FESOM (top row) and ICON (bottom row) simulations, for the first decade of the simulations (2020-2029, left column) and changes in annual mean capacity factor relative to first decade for 2030-2039 (middle column) and 2040-2049 (right column)

regulation of sensitive areas and long-term planning for technological impacts. The distributed scenario emphasised social equity and decentralised governance, calling for simplified regulation, citizen compensation schemes, and local ownership of energy infrastructure.

Participants acknowledged that km-scale modelling offered new possibilities for informing planning at regional and metropolitan scales, particularly by enabling the localisation of trends in wind and solar potential. The visualisations helped to ground abstract climate data in place-specific contexts. However, some participants found the capacity factor an imperfect indicator for their operational needs, preferring access to more basic variables such as wind speed or solar irradiance. There was also a strong demand for improved integration across systems—linking energy to water, biodiversity, and land-use planning.

Despite the uncertainties inherent in climate modelling, stakeholders recognised the added value of high-resolution simulations in increasing the robustness of long-term planning. They also expressed interest in using the models not just as data sources but as boundary tools to facilitate cross-sectoral dialogue. The iterative workshops created a space for shared learning and trust-building, with some stakeholders noting that their understanding of the roles and dependencies among actors in the energy transition had evolved. The discussions also reinforced the notion that many decisions are made despite uncertainties—and that making such uncertainties explicit, rather than hiding them, can support more resilient governance.

The results of the integration workshop demonstrate that participatory storyline processes, when coupled with km-scale climate modelling, can generate actionable insights and reveal synergies and tensions across sectors. They also show how this co-productive approach can shape future climate modelling efforts by identifying what information is relevant, at what scales, and for whom.

5 Discussion

This deliverable presents the integration of stakeholder-defined storylines with high-resolution climate model data. To conduct the study, each narrative was translated into spatially explicit constraints applied to the same underlying set of model simulations. All scenarios used outputs from the same ICON and IFS-FESOM km-scale simulations (2020–2050, SSP3-7.0) and did not differ in their climate inputs. Instead, differences across the "Actual", "Integrative", and "Distributive" scenarios were operationalized through spatial masking and post-processing of the physical outputs. For example, the "Integrative" storyline applied biodiversity exclusion zones (from the Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition's zonification maps) to mask areas deemed environmentally sensitive. Similarly, the "Distributive" scenario focused exclusively on rooftop solar by incorporating data on roof surface availability. This approach preserved the physical consistency of the climate simulations while enabling exploration of how different societal choices influence renewable energy deployment potential.

All simulations were run using the storm-resolving Earth system models ICON and IFS-FESOM at kilometre-scale resolution, with climate data extracted for variables directly relevant to renewable energy planning. Specifically, wind speed (at 10 m and 100 m), solar radiation (global horizontal irradiance), air temperature, wind speed, and precipitation were processed into capacity factors for wind and solar PV production. The high spatial resolution of the models was key to identifying regional and even sub-regional variations in resource availability, which are critical for decision-making. While this deliverable did not include a side-by-side comparison with coarser resolution models, the masks applied at fine scale (e.g., Natura 2000 boundaries, rooftop fractions) demonstrate a granularity in planning that would be impossible to replicate with standard GCMs or even downscaled CMIP6 outputs. This highlights the added value of km-scale modelling not only in simulating weather and climate extremes, but also in informing operational decisions such as technology siting and trade-off analysis between land use, biodiversity, and energy equity.

This study thus demonstrates the potential of combining kilometre-scale Earth system models (km-ESMs) with participatory storyline methodologies to bridge the gap between advanced climate science and decision-making in the context of the renewable energy transition. By coupling high-resolution climate simulations with co-produced narratives that reflect societal priorities and concerns, we created a framework that not only provides detailed physical climate information but also makes this information more meaningful and usable for diverse stakeholder groups. The use of km-ESMs allowed us to represent fine-scale climate processes that are crucial for regional energy planning, such as spatial variability in wind and solar resources, and to explore how these might evolve under different socio-political choices. Also, differences between models were helpful in explaining climate science more generally.

Our integration of stakeholder co-produced scenarios with model outputs revealed several important insights. First, participants valued the ability of km-scale models to provide geographically specific data, supporting regional and metropolitan planning for renewable energy deployment. However, the results also highlighted that advanced resolution alone is insufficient to address decision-making needs; stakeholders require climate information to be linked clearly to operational, regulatory, and socio-economic contexts. The capacity factor maps and scenario

analyses were seen as useful heuristic tools, helping to visualise trade-offs between energy production, biodiversity protection, and social equity. However, stakeholders emphasised the need for models and indicators that connect more directly to sectoral concerns, such as grid stability, water-energy interactions, and socio-economic impacts.

Notably, the study shows that km-ESMs and scenario storylines can function effectively as boundary objects, enabling dialogue across disciplinary and sectoral boundaries. The mixed-methods approach fostered shared understanding and surfaced knowledge gaps that purely technical analyses might overlook. For example, discussions revealed strong interest in modelling interactions between climate trends and land use change, as well as the effects of climate extremes on energy infrastructure. They also highlighted persistent challenges, including the difficulty of integrating long-term climate projections into planning cycles, the uncertainties associated with model divergence, and the lack of operational tools that bridge climate science with energy and environmental policy.

Overall, this work underscores the value of combining quantitative climate modelling with qualitative scenario building to enhance the relevance, legitimacy, and usability of climate information, in this case, for the renewable energy transition. It also points to future priorities, including expanding to additional case studies, exploring other emission pathways, and coupling km-scale climate projections with detailed impact models. Moving forward, sustained collaboration between climate scientists, social scientists, and decision-makers will be essential to ensure that emerging modelling tools such as km-ESMs truly support just and sustainable energy futures.

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